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Impact Factor: 2.625

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.581479

DOI URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.581479>

Cite this paper as : Hartesh Pannu (2017). *THE IMPACT OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT INFRASTRUCTURE ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN SMES*, *International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research*, ISSN: 2349 –3593 (online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (print), Vol.4,(Issue2, Feb-2017), pp 26–pp 31, DOI URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.581479>

THE IMPACT OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT INFRASTRUCTURE ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN SMES

Ms. Hartesh Pannu

Assistant Professor

Chandigarh Group of Colleges Landran, Mohali, Punjab, India

Abstract

Knowledge management is recognized as an important weapon for sustaining competitive advantage and improving performance. The evaluation of knowledge management (KM) performance has become increasingly important since it provides the reference for directing the organizations to enhance their performance and competitiveness. This study aims to determine the impact of knowledge management infrastructure on the Organizational Performance in SMEs that need knowledge to perform their work and tasks. . Organizations should establish knowledge directorates to discover and transmit knowledge to workers with a view to improve the creativeness and distinctiveness of organizations. The use of KM practices can contribute to the overall growth of SMEs by simultaneously and significantly enhancing their performance. The findings indicated that there was a strong effect of knowledge management infrastructure on the Organizational Performance.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Infrastructure, Performance, Effectiveness, Organizational Culture/ Structure, Information Technology, Shared Knowledge, SMEs.

Introduction :

Knowledge is one of the most vital assets that guaranteed the survival of firms in the fiercely competitive business environment. The emergence of knowledge-based economy has made it a strategic necessity for businesses to initiate ways to effectively acquire and manage varying organizational knowledge. Knowledge when produced and disseminated all over the organization has the capability to contribute to the firm's value (Choi et al., 2006). Ineffectiveness in managing knowledge makes the knowledge irrelevant and not useful for organizations (Yusof & Abu Bakar, 2012). Hence, knowledge management (KM) is considered to be an urgent and critical issue, to such an extent that organizations must efficiently manage their knowledge bases and repositories to earn long-term competitive advantage (Alabi & Leidner, 1999; Devenport & Prusak, 1998). The application of KM strategy offers firms with active potentials for enhancing knowledge quality and for consolidating the value and applicability of knowledge (Spender & Grant, 1996). Knowledge management process capabilities were conceptualized as four dimensional constructs: knowledge acquisition, knowledge conversion, knowledge application, and knowledge protection while organizational performance were divided into two dimensions namely, non-financial performance and financial performance.

Generally, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in supporting the nation's economy. The purpose of this study is to provide valuable insights to SME's through knowledge management using its key contributing factors (effectiveness, increasing productivity and efficiency of operations) towards establishing effective knowledge management Given the importance of knowledge, entrepreneurs are encouraged to develop their capabilities to manage knowledge which will move them to become more competitive and innovative.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the role of knowledge infrastructure capability in knowledge management (KM) practices within an organization.

Framework-

1. Knowledge Management

Knowledge management infrastructure reflects the long-term foundations for information and knowledge management. In an organizational context, the infrastructure includes five major components:

- organization culture
- organization structure
- organization's information technology infrastructure
- common knowledge
- physical environment (Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010).

1.1 Knowledge Management and organization culture-

Organizational culture is a strategic business practice in which the principles and values of an organization emerge (Robbins, DeCenzo, & Gao, 2007; Zheng, Yang, & McLean, 2010). Culture is defined as a pattern of basic assumptions that a group has created, discovered, or developed by learning to cope with problems and teaching new members the means by which to solve the problems correctly (Schein, 1990, 2010; Shafritz, Ott, & Jang, 2015). It is also considered the pool of knowledge that differentiates employees in an organization (Cavaliere & Lombardi, 2015; Hofstede, Hofstede, & Minkov, 2010). The organizational process of KM culture is one of the best corporate strategies for the transfer of information and is a factor in success or failure (Bartol & Srivastava, 2002; W.-B. Lin, 2008; S. Wang & Noe, 2010). When employees have a culture of sharing and transfer valuable information in the enterprise, corporate objectives are accomplished (Foss, Husted, & Michailova, 2010; Michailova, McCarthy, Puffer, May, & Stewart Jr, 2013). In addition, when the culture of information sharing is promoted and encouraged, prominent competitive advantage can be achieved (Abdul-Jalal, Toulson, & Tweed, 2013; Jelavic, 2011; Parjanen, 2012). A small company must focus on the harmony of a corporate philosophy based on values that allow employees to commit to the proper use of information in database systems for customers, suppliers, and staff. These practices contribute significantly to the improvement of innovation processes (Dixit & Nanda, 2011; Maheshwarkar & Sohani, 2013).

1.2 Knowledge Management and organization structure-

Organizational structures deal with the way the firm is organized, and the way people relate to one another. Broadly speaking, there are two types of organizational structure, namely formal and informal. These two concepts are not

independent, and the formal structure may greatly influence informal networks, both positively and negatively. The focus of KM in an organization is found within many different management functions - human resources, IT, information management (library), marketing and R&D to name but a few. However, in an organizationwide KM programme its tentacles should reach out into all parts of the organization. This is best achieved through some kind of networked organization structure. Various terms such as 'spider's web', lattice organization, hypertext organization, clustered webs, federation of business units, Team Nets have been used.

1.3 Knowledge Management and organization's information technology infrastructure-

Knowledge management is also facilitated by the organization's Information Technology Infrastructure. Although certain information technologies and systems are directly developed to pursue knowledge management, the organization's overall Information Technology Infrastructure, developed to support the organization's information systems needs, also facilitates knowledge management. The Information Technology Infrastructure is the combination of data processing, storage, and communication technologies and systems (databases, servers, computers, information devices, etc) and the processes that make it all work. It comprises the entire spectrum of organization's information systems, including transaction processing systems and management information systems. It consists of databases and data warehouses, as well as enterprise resource planning systems.

1.4 Knowledge Management and common knowledge-

Common Knowledge represents another important component of the infrastructure that enables knowledge management. It refers to the organization's cumulative experiences in comprehending a category of knowledge and activities and the organizing principles that support communication and coordination (Zander and Kogut 1995, as cited in Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010).

Common knowledge provides unity to the organization. It includes:

- a common language and vocabulary
- recognition of individual knowledge domains
- common cognitive schema
- shared norms, and elements of specialized knowledge that are common across individuals sharing knowledge (Grant, 1996; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998, as cited in Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010).

Common knowledge helps enhance the value of an individual expert's knowledge by integrating it with the knowledge of others.

1.5 Knowledge Management and physical environment-

The physical environment within the organization is often taken for granted, but it is another important foundation upon which knowledge management rests. Key aspects of the physical environment include:

- the design of buildings and the separation between them
- the location, size, and type of offices
- the type, number, and nature of meeting rooms; and so on.

Physical environment can foster knowledge management by providing opportunities for employees to meet and share ideas. Coffee rooms, cafeterias, water coolers, and hallways do provide venues where employees learn from and share insights with each other.

2. Organizational Performance

Organizational performance reflects the ability of an organization to fulfil its stakeholders' requirements and survive in the market (Griffin, 2003). It is also known as the outcome of the actions or activities carried out by the members of organization to measure how well an organization has accomplished its objectives (Ho, 2008; Chung & Lo, 2007).

Organizational performance is usually measured by the actual output or result of organization against its intended output – goals or objective, or how well a company achieves their objectives. The measure of firm's performance may include financial performance and economic performance (efficiency). There is a difference between profitability and efficiency, which depends on market conditions and goals pursued by managers. It means higher efficiency may not necessarily translate into higher profitability. In organizational context, performance may link with growth through improvement in efficiency, productivity, quality, market share, etc. It is implied that organizational performance can be assessed by organization's efficiency and effectiveness of goal achievement. As mentioned earlier, it is stated that the concept of effectiveness is a ratio, implying that two entities are required when defining and measuring effectiveness. He also argued that when effectiveness is conceptualized as a degree of goal attainment, that is, the achievement of profitability goal.

3. SMEs

SME sector of India is considered as the backbone of economy contributing to 45% of the industrial output, 40% of India's exports, employing 60 million people, create 1.3 million jobs every year and produce more than 8000 quality products for the Indian and international markets. With approximately 30 million SME's in India, the sector is growing at a rate of 8% per year and Government of India is taking different measures to increase their competitiveness in the international market.

Despite of so much growth in Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME's) still, they are having implicit knowledge and limited resources due to which the knowledge is insufficiently shared between managers and other employees. So, in the context of SME's, knowledge management can be used to capture knowledge and experience generated during their operations, activities and processes. But it is a well known fact that SME's play a significant role in Nation development through high contribution to domestic production, significant export earnings, low investment requirements, operational flexibility, location wise mobility, low intensive imports, capacities to develop appropriate indigenous technology, import substitution, contribution towards defence, production, technology, competitiveness in domestic and export markets thereby generating new entrepreneurs by providing knowledge and trainings.

SME's tend to have a more organic and fluid culture, than larger organizations. Smaller number of people usually united under common beliefs and values which implies that it is easier for smaller organizations to change and implement knowledge management. It is easier to create a knowledge sharing culture in smaller organization than in larger ones. In smaller organizations the cultural values and beliefs of the employees can be influenced by the owners. This can be a problem if the owner does not trust his employees or does not encourage the culture of sharing and transferring knowledge. So, knowledge management plays a pivotal role in such situations.

Conclusion

The result shows that knowledge is managed on people-based-approach in SMEs. Given SMEs characteristics mainly owned by local people, labor intensive, workers and entrepreneurs are low educated, and financing their

operations from personal savings – acquisition of knowledge in SMEs are mainly achieved by networking with other organization such as companies, universities, technical colleges, and government agencies through alliances. This study also indicates that KM infrastructure has effected the organizational performance of SMEs and most of the managers have an optimistic thought on their company’s future. These findings have some similarities with the study of KM in large companies although they have different characteristic in nature and in managing knowledge. SMEs should ponder how KM can be implemented successfully. This would include strategies and programs for implementing KM, and encouraging learning and knowledge sharing among employees. A key element of KM is to enhance the learning capacity of the firm. One way to do so is by building a learning organization. This is more related to designing organizational procedures and routines than it is to managing assets. On the basis of the analysis this study we can conclude that KM capabilities can play an important role in the organizational performance of SME’s

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